

Filling the gap between design and construction phases when using BIM in the MEP sector

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Abstract

MEP systems which contain large numbers of elements, components, and equipment face a gap between the design and the installation phases. This gap comes from detailed design models and documentation that are not well prepared, way of collaboration, communication, workflow, installation, way of ordering system and model checking. In this way, specific factors like the size of the components, available space for installing, walking, transporting and maintaining, the delivery time of equipment, and possible clashes make the processes in the MEP sector more sensitive than in other parts of a building. In this regard, finding ways for connecting the BIM model between design and installation, while covering the identified gaps, makes the processes in the MEP sector more efficient.

4D and 5D modelling with schedules and costs connected to the components helps managers, coordinators, and planners to make more realistic decisions. Moreover, it gives more control over the project timeline and the cost of each decision for selecting the best alternative. As the MEP process comprises a dynamic set of activities, it is crucial to have an overview on it before starting a project. In this way, the data and model that are prepared can be more understandable for various groups that want to use the output of one group as an input for the next step in another group. In addition, defining a local CDE (static data) and a shared CDE (dynamic data) for the companies involved in a project makes the data more accessible

and available for the next usage.

In this regard, software research, before selecting an alternative, plays a crucial role in a well-connected model for installation. It is important to select a platform that can cover the requirements of the companies, help various groups to have access to the latest version of documents, request more information, assign tasks to the target groups, and check the status of component orders in real time. As a result, both the selection tool and the way of modelling help managers to make the MEP project optimized and standardized.

This research used Navisworks for adding the schedules and costs to the BIM model which required defined parameters in Revit and MS Project. Then for connecting the BIM model to the construction phase Dalux has been used. 4D and 5D modelling are proposed as a way of working in the MEP sector to give more control to managers and planer for optimized installation. Moreover, the status of the ordering list has been connected to Navisworks for real-time status of orders checking. Dalux as a viewing platform has been used for model checking, measurement, progress checking, task assigning, adding annotations and photos to plans, dynamic CDE, capturing, workflow creation, and meetings.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/gLVPP2sDGyU>

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